

EBFMC25-OOP-13 · Evaluating the Predictive Value of Lumbar Puncture in Normal Pressure Hydrocephalus

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15828317>

Online Oral Presentation #13 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: *Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress*.

AUTHORS

Mehdi Hekimoglu
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1182-2216>

AFFILIATIONS

Amerikan Hospital
Neurosurgery Department
Istanbul, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Idiopathic Normal Pressure Hydrocephalus (INPH) is a syndrome in the elderly characterized by gait disturbance, cognitive decline, and urinary incontinence. Although considered potentially reversible, not all patients respond to treatment. Shunt surgery often improves symptoms, but the predictive value of post-lumbar puncture (LP) gait response remains unclear (Bloch & McDermott, 2012; Cui et al., 2021). This study investigates whether patients without improvement after LP can still benefit from shunt surgery, reassessing LP's reliability as a predictive tool.

Materials and Methods: A total of 48 patients (mean age: 67.5; 27 males, 21 females) clinically and radiologically diagnosed with INPH were evaluated between 2021 and 2023. All patients underwent standardized gait assessments before and after LP. Based on their post-LP gait response, they were divided into two groups: Group A (those who improved) and Group B (those who did not improve). All patients subsequently received lumboperitoneal shunt surgery. Clinical outcomes, including gait function, cognition, and urinary symptoms, were reassessed three months postoperatively.

Results: Postoperative gait improvement was observed in 88% of Group A and 73.9% of Group B. Both groups showed partial improvement in urinary and cognitive symptoms. While the improvement rate was higher in patients who responded positively to LP, a statistically significant portion of non-responders also benefited from surgery ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: While a positive gait response to LP is a useful predictor of shunt success, it should not be the sole criterion. Patients without improvement may still benefit from surgery. These results indicate that LP alone is insufficient to guide treatment decisions (Klinge et al., 2005) and must be considered with broader clinical context. This finding is especially relevant for family physicians, who play a key role in early recognition, referral, and longitudinal care of elderly patients with suspected INPH.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Normal pressure hydrocephalus, lumbar puncture, shunt surgery, gait disturbance, elderly

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Bloch, Orin, and Michael W McDermott. "Lumbo-peritoneal shunts for the treatment of normal pressure hydrocephalus." *Journal of clinical neuroscience: official journal of the Neurosurgical Society of Australasia* vol. 19,8 (2012): 1107-11. doi:10.1016/j.jocn.2011.11.019

Cui, Wenyao et al. "Comparison of ventriculoperitoneal shunt to lumbo-peritoneal shunt in the treatment of idiopathic: A monocentric, assessor blinded, randomized controlled trial." *Medicine* vol. 100,31 (2021): e26691. doi:10.1097/MD.00000000000026691

Klinge, Petra et al. "Outcome of shunting in idiopathic normal-pressure hydrocephalus and the value of outcome assessment in shunted patients." *Neurosurgery* vol. 57,3 Suppl (2005): S40-52; discussion ii-v. doi:10.1227/01.neu.0000168187.01077.2f

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Mehdi Hekimoglu

Amerikan Hospital

Neurosurgery Department

Istanbul, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1182-2216>

mehdih@amerikanhastanesi.org